

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Rice remains from Neolithic Age excavated in China

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China is one of the first countries in which rice was farmed. One hundred nine Neolithic remains of rice culture in China, dating back to 1050-5850 BC, have been studied. Carbonated grains were most commonly excavated.

Forty-nine of the samples date to 1050-2550 BC, 43 to 2550-4050 BC, and 17 to 4050-5850 BC. Eighty-two of the remains, including the three oldest at Luojiajiao, Hemudu, and Pengtoushan, were discovered in the middle and lower basins of the Yangtze River (see figure).

Thousands of carbonated whole grains, leaves, and stems were found in

Hemudu. Based on length, width and shape of grains, and characteristics of awns, the grains were identified as cultivated indicas and japonicas and a few types of wild rice (*O. rufipogon* Griff). In Luojiajiao, the grains originated from japonicas.

Many carbonated grains and hulls were discovered in unearthed pottery in Pengtoushan. Some scientists think these are grains of cultivated rice.

Based on these findings, rice farming may have been developed as long as 8,500 years ago in the middle and lower basins of the Yangtze River. ■

Distribution of excavated rice remains from the Neolithic Age in China.

Breeding methods

Effect of seedling age on flowering of cytoplasmic male sterile and restorer lines of rice

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Nonsynchronized flowering of parental lines, unavailable area-specific seed production technology, and difficulty in arranging adequate isolation make hybrid rice seed production challenging. We manipulated seedling age of some cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) and restorer lines (prospective parents of promising hybrids) to synchronize flowering.

Four CMS and eight restorer lines were studied during 1992 wet season. The nursery was transplanted when seedlings were 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, and 45 d old. Data were recorded at initiation of panicle emergence, 50% flowering, and complete flowering. Days to flowering were calculated from transplanting date.

Seedling age affects panicle emergence in both CMS and restorer lines (see figure). Panicle emergence tended to be delayed in the 20- and 25-d-old seedlings but was quicker in those 35-45 d old. In general, panicle emergence was advanced or delayed by half the number of days difference in seedling age compared with a 30-d-old seedling. Data at panicle emergence correlated with those at 50% flowering and complete flowering.

In genotypes IR58025 A, IR13292 R, PAU1106-21-3 R, and PAU1106-21-4 R, panicle emergence was delayed or advanced by as many days as there was difference between seedling age and a 30-d-old seedling. Genetic differences among genotypes in the ability of seedlings to establish after transplanting, might cause this difference in panicle emergence. ■